

SOP

Standardized protocol for resazurin-based viability assays on P-MSC/TER308 cells in 2D culture

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Scope Step-by-step protocol to assay viability on P-MSC/TERT308 cell line in 2D culture using a resazurin-based method with optimized parameters to ensure consistent results with a measurement uncertainty <10%.		

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Introduction

In Europe, a significant percentage of neonatal and infant deaths are attributed to preterm births, with approximately 75% of neonatal deaths and 60% of infant deaths occurring in preterm infants [1]. The rising number of preterm births is influenced by factors such as advanced maternal age, environmental threats, and limited suitable treatments.

The LifeSaver project (<https://lifesaverproject.eu/>), funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, aims to support every pregnant woman to have a safe living environment, protected by scientifically justified regulations governing the use and control of potentially harmful chemical and medicinal products. The project objective is to create a digitally cloned *in vitro* system that emulates prenatal conditions near the uterine/placental interface, contributing with a scientifically-based tool for screening and analyzing chemicals and pharmaceuticals, aiding in risk classification, regulations, and risk assessment/mitigation measures for pregnant women and fetal health.

In this context, it is crucial to note the recent emphasis on the presence of data inconsistencies in pre-clinical studies [2–5]. This inconsistency hampers result comparisons and raises concerns about the reliability of findings.

To improve the reliability of pharmacological and toxicity screening for drugs and environmental contaminants, as a part of this ambitious project, efforts are dedicated to optimizing cellular cytotoxicity assays. To this end, the resazurin-based assay has been selected as the primary method. Indeed, the resazurin-based viability assay is one of the most adopted tools to assess drug cytotoxicity. Exploiting the ability of living cells to reduce the non-fluorescent dye resazurin into fluorescent resorufin, this assay provides a reliable indicator of cellular metabolic activity and, consequently, cell viability. The simplicity and sensitivity of the resazurin assay make it particularly advantageous for assessing the cytotoxic effects of various substances on several cell lines [6]. Its versatility extends to high-throughput screening applications, enabling the rapid evaluation of several compounds and concentrations.

Aims

The primary objective of this Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) is to enhance the results reliability of the resazurin-based cytotoxicity test conducted on the P-MSC/TER308 cell line, a placenta-derived mesenchymal stem cell line employed in the LifeSaver project. To address this aim, we applied our previously established and validated INRIM_SOP Bio_001 [7]. The adherence to this SOP ensures to obtain consistent results with a measurement uncertainty less than 10%.

Terminology

In the following SOP, the term “must” is used to denote mandatory steps or requirements within the protocol. When "must" is employed, adherence is non-negotiable, as these actions are essential for the correct execution and reliability of the procedure. Conversely, the term "should" has been employed to highlight recommended practices that, while not mandatory, are strongly advised for achieving optimal results.

List of abbreviations

FC, Fold Change; FI, Fluorescent Intensity; h, Hours; λ_{Em} , Emission Wavelength; λ_{Ex} , Excitation Wavelength; minutes, min; PBS, Phosphate Buffered Saline; RT, Room Temperature; SD, Standard Deviation; SOP, Standard Operating Procedure; WS, Working Solution.

Materials

Equipment

- Standard equipment for cell culture (e.g., centrifuge for tubes, cell incubator, laminar flow hood, optical microscope, micropipettes, etc.);
- Cell counting chamber or automatic cell counter;
- Fluorescence reader with monochromator or suitable wavelength filters.

Consumables

- Cell culture plates;
- 96-well plate for fluorescence measurements (e.g., black plates);
- Centrifuge tubes (15 and 50 mL);
- Microtubes (1.5 and 2 mL);
- Pipette tips;
- Serological Pipettes;
- 0.22 µm filter;
- Syringes.

Reagents

- Cell culture medium: MSC NutriStem XF Basal Medium (Sartorius);
- Cell culture medium supplements to support cell growth and viability: MSC NutriStem XF Supplement Mix (Sartorius), Geneticin (G418), and NutriCoat Attachment Solution (Sartorius);
- TrypLE Select Enzyme (Thermo Fisher Scientific);
- milliQ-H₂O;
- Resazurin sodium salt;
- Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS)
- Ringer Solution.

General information

Unless stated otherwise, all procedures should be performed under sterile laminar flow conditions. Protective gloves and lab coat should be worn, and all work areas should be thoroughly cleaned before and after testing. Resazurin should be handled following standard laboratory safety protocols, and all waste should be disposed according to institutional biosafety guidelines.

Experimental workflow

1. Dissolve resazurin powder into Mill-Q H₂O to an appropriate concentration (e.g., 4.4 mM or 440 μM), sterilize by filtration through a 0.22 μm filter, and prepare aliquots to store at -20°C;
2. Prepare complete MSC NutriStem XF medium: MSC NutriStem XF Basal Medium, MSC NutriStem XF Supplement Mix, and 200 μg/ml G418, following the [manufacturer's recommended protocols](#);
3. Pre-coat plate/flask with NutriCoat Attachment Solution, following the [instructions of the manufacturer](#). Briefly, dilute the substrate 1:500 in Ringer Solution and transfer the diluted substrate to the culture flasks (72 μl/cm²), incubate at least 1 hour (h) at 37°C.
4. Remove and discard exhaust culture medium from cells;
5. Wash the cells twice with 1x PBS (each 160 μl/cm²);
6. Add TrypLE Select Enzyme solution (20 μl/cm²) to the plate and incubate the culture flask at 37°C for approximately 2-3 minutes (min);
7. As soon as all cells are detached (if necessary, agitate the cells by gently hitting the flask), add growth medium (about 160 μl/cm²) and centrifuge at 180 g for 5 min;
8. Discard the supernatant, resuspend the cell pellet in the remaining droplet and add growth medium (about 160 μl/cm²);
9. Seed an adequate number of cells in the multi-well plate chosen for the experiment. 70-80% cell confluency¹ (2.4-2.7×10⁴ cells/cm²) is recommended to test compounds cytotoxicity; while 15-30% cell confluency (0.5-1×10⁴ cells/cm²) is suggested for proliferation assays;
10. Include the following control samples:
 - a. Untreated Cells Control: wells with untreated cells to serve as a “starting point”, for cell proliferation experiments, or as a “100% living cell point”, for cytotoxicity tests. Add the same solvent used to deliver the test compounds;
 - b. Positive Control: wells containing cells treated with a known cell-proliferation-inducing compound for cell growth tests or a highly toxic substance (e.g., 10% DMSO) in cytotoxicity tests;
11. Culture cells until they are firmly attached to the bottom of the plate using standard cell culture conditions (recommended time: 8 h);
12. Gently remove the complete medium from the well and treat cells with the test compound (e.g., growth factors, cytokines, or cytotoxic compounds) for a period of time that depends on your experiments (usually, 24-72 h);
13. After culturing cells for the desired exposure period, allow resazurin to reach room temperature (RT). A 37°C water bath may be used to eventually thaw the reagent. Protect the resazurin from direct light;
14. Prepare the resazurin working solution (WS) with a concentration of 44 μM in the complete cells culture medium and warm it at 37°C until use;
15. Remove the assay plate from the incubator and gently eliminate the medium from the wells;

¹ Cell confluency is the degree to which the surface of a cell-culture dish is covered by adherent cells [8].

16. Add an appropriate volume of resazurin WS in each well (test and control wells). The volume of resazurin WS depends on the multi-well plate used. Refer to the table below to select the correct resazurin WS volume² (Table 1)

Culture plate	Surface area [cm ²]	Resazurin WS volume [mL]
96-well	0.32	0.1
48-well	1.1	0.35
24-well	1.9	0.6
12-well	3.5	1.1
6-well	9.6	3

Table 1. Resazurin WS volumes recommended for different multi-well plates in order to maintain the scalability ratio.

17. The following additional control samples are recommended in each experiment:
- No-Cell Control (Blank): resazurin WS only (Nutriccoat pre-coated wells without cells to serve as the negative control to determine fluorescent intensity (FI) background);
 - Test Compound Control: wells without cells containing the solvent and compound to test for possible chemical interference with resazurin;
 - Empty wells (two or more) in the 96-well plate for FI detection: empty wells should display a minimal FI signal. This control sample is useful to verify that the plate reader is working correctly³.
18. Incubate cells using standard culture conditions. To select the optimal incubation time, refer to the following recommendations (Table 2):

Cell n°/Area [cm ²]	Incubation time [h]
4×10 ² - 2×10 ³	6
2×10 ³ - 1.7×10 ⁴	4
1.7×10 ⁴ - 3.5×10 ⁴	2

Table 2. Resazurin incubation time recommended for different cell concentrations.⁴

19. Reached the expected incubation time, gently remove the resazurin WS from the respective wells and transfer 100 µL in a 96-well plate for FI measurement (black plate);
20. Use a Fluorescence Microplate Reader to record the FI at an excitation wavelength (λ_{Ex}) of 535 nm and an emission wavelength (λ_{Em}) of 590 nm;

² In line with the recommended volume of 100 µL/well for the 96-well plate, the volumes suggested for the other plates are proportionally adjusted based on their well surface area. This ensures that, regardless of the surface, cells may receive and metabolize an equivalent amount of Resazurin. Consequently, this approach guarantees the comparability of results obtained across different plates.

³ This control sample is optional, but recommended at least in the first experiments.

⁴ The incubation time is inversely proportional to the number of cells.

21. Calculate the FI_{mean} and standard deviation (SD) of replicates for each test condition (test and controls wells);
22. Subtract the FI_{mean} of Blank from the FI_{mean} of all experimental wells ($FI_{\text{Sample-Blank}}$);
23. Calculate the SD ($FI_{\text{Sample-Blank}}$) by propagating the error using the formula:

$$SD(FI_{\text{Sample-Blank}}) = \sqrt{SD_{\text{Sample}}^2 + SD_{\text{Blank}}^2}$$

Results quantification

Relative quantification

For proliferation assays, results are usually expressed as fold change (FC, a measure that describes how much a quantity changes between an original and a subsequent measurement [8]), normalizing results on “Untreated Cells Control” using the equation:

$$\text{Cell growth}_{FC} = \frac{FI_{\text{Compound}}}{FI_{\text{Untreat Cells Control}}}$$

FI_{Compound} = FI values of cells treated with different concentrations of compound

$FI_{\text{Untreated Cells Control}}$ = FI value of Untreated Cells Control

For cytotoxicity tests, results are usually expressed as percentage, normalizing on control samples by setting the Untreated Cells Control as “100% living cell point” and the Positive Control as “0% living cell point”, applying the following formula (“min-max normalization” method, also called “feature scaling”):

$$z_s = \left(\frac{x_s - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \right) \times 100$$

z_s = normalized value of the sample in the dataset

x_s = value of the sample in the dataset

$\min(x)$ = the minimum value in the dataset (Positive Control)

$\max(x)$ = the maximum value in the dataset (Untreated Cells Control)

Absolute quantification

Calibration curve preparation:

1. In a range between 6 and 12 h before the conclusion of the experiment, detach cells as indicated above;
2. Resuspend cells in an appropriate volume of medium and count them;
3. Prepare at least 5 cell serial dilutions in a complete culture medium. The standard concentrations should at least cover the range of estimated concentrations for the unknown test samples and be evenly spaced throughout the range⁵ [9];

⁵ For a more convenient estimation of the calibration curve range, consult literature data, focusing on specific parameters relevant to the experiment type (e.g., cell duplication time under normal conditions, IC50, or LD50 of the tested compound).

4. Seed the cell dilutions in a multi-well plate (at least triplicate wells for each condition are recommended);
5. Culture cells until they are firmly attached to the bottom of the plate using standard cell culture conditions.

Cell concentration evaluation:

6. Simultaneously with the addition of resazurin WS to the experiment samples, treat the calibration curve equally;
7. Reached the expected incubation time, gently remove the resazurin WS from the wells and transfer 100 μ L in a 96-well plate for FI measurement;
8. Use a Fluorescence Microplate Reader to record the FI at λ_{EX} : 535 nm and λ_{EM} : 590 nm;
9. Calculate the FI_{mean} and SD of replicate for each test condition (calibration curve, unknown samples, and controls);
10. Subtract the FI_{mean} of Blank from the FI_{mean} of all experimental wells and calibration curve ($FI_{Sample-Blank}$);
11. Calculate the SD ($FI_{Sample-Blank}$) by propagating the error using the formula:

$$SD(FI_{Sample-Blank}) = \sqrt{SD_{Sample}^2 + SD_{Blank}^2}$$

12. For the calibration curve, plot $FI_{Sample-Blank}$ (y-axis) versus the number of cells seeded (x-axis; e.g., cell n° /well or cell n° /cm²);
13. Calculate the linear equation resulting from the calibration curve. Check that R^2 is higher than 0.97. If R^2 is lower, repeat the experiment or exclude one or more points of the curve, avoiding having a calibration curve with less than 5 points;
14. Use the resulting linear equation to estimate the cell concentration of unknown samples by interpolating their $FI_{Sample-Blank}$ values (y values) as follow:

$$x = \frac{y - b}{m}$$

x : cell concentration of the unknown sample (unknown variable)
 y : $FI_{Sample-Blank}$ of the unknown sample
 b : y-intercept of the linear equation derived from the calibration curve
 m : slope (S) of the linear equation derived from the calibration curve

15. If the cell concentration values obtained for unknown samples were outside the calibration curve range, it is recommended to repeat the experiment by varying the calibration curve range.

N.B.: A calibration curve must be used in each independent experiment and must be incubated with resazurin WS under identical conditions as the unknown and control samples.

Test parameters

Test parameters	Values
Limit of Blank (LoB)	~18 cell/cm ²
Limit of Detection (LoD)	~1.25×10 ² cell/cm ²
Limit of Quantification (LoQ)	~4×10 ² cell/cm ²
Mean Relative Repeatability	2.2%
Mean Relative Reproducibility	4.3%
Mean Relative Expanded Uncertainty	9.8%
Suitable for time lapse experiments	Yes

Table 2. Test parameters⁶ associated with the specific protocol outlined in this SOP

References

- [1] M. Delnord, B. Blondel, J. Zeitlin, What contributes to disparities in the preterm birth rate in European countries?, *Current Opinion in Obstetrics & Gynecology* 27 (2015) 133–142. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GCO.0000000000000156>.
- [2] B. Haibe-Kains, N. El-Hachem, N.J. Birkbak, A.C. Jin, A.H. Beck, H.J.W.L. Aerts, J. Quackenbush, Inconsistency in large pharmacogenomic studies, *Nature* 504 (2013) 389–393. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12831>.
- [3] L.P. Freedman, I.M. Cockburn, T.S. Simcoe, The Economics of Reproducibility in Preclinical Research, *PLoS Biol* 13 (2015) e1002165. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002165>.
- [4] F. Prinz, T. Schlange, K. Asadullah, Believe it or not: how much can we rely on published data on potential drug targets?, *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 10 (2011) 712–712. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd3439-c1>.
- [5] P. Horvath, N. Aulner, M. Bickle, A.M. Davies, E.D. Nery, D. Ebner, M.C. Montoya, P. Östling, V. Pietiäinen, L.S. Price, S.L. Shorte, G. Turcatti, C. Von Schantz, N.O. Carragher, Screening out irrelevant cell-based models of disease, *Nat Rev Drug Discov* 15 (2016) 751–769. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd.2016.175>.
- [6] D. Lavogina, H. Lust, M.-J. Tahk, T. Laasfeld, H. Vellama, N. Nasirova, M. Vardja, K.-L. Eskla, A. Salumets, A. Rincken, J. Jaal, Revisiting the Resazurin-Based Sensing of Cellular Viability: Widening the Application Horizon, *Biosensors* 12 (2022) 196. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios12040196>.
- [7] J. Petiti, L. Revel, C. Divieto, Standard Operating Procedure to Optimize Resazurin-Based Viability Assays, *Biosensors* 14 (2024) 156. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios14040156>.
- [8] E.J. Borowski, J.M. Borwein, *Collins dictionary of Mathematics*, Collins Dictionary of Mathematics (2012).
- [9] V. Barwick, *Preparation of Calibration Curves - A Guide to Best Practice*, (2003). <https://www.lgcgroup.com/media/2997/preparation-of-calibration-curves.pdf?ipignore=true>.

⁶ Refer to the main text for parameter definitions and calculation.